

SOCIO-POLITICAL LIFE IN THE KOKAND KHANATE

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At the beginning of the 18th century, a new state formed in the Fergana Valley - the Kokand Khanate - was founded by a thousand tribes representing the local population. For example, the depression of the political and social life of the Ashtarkhanids in the late seventeenth and early eighteenth centuries, the growth of economic independence of the Fergana Valley and the revolt of the Chodak lords in 1704 and the occupation of part of Fergana created the conditions for this. However, the territories of Kasan, Asht, and Chodak in the north and northwest of Fergana were under the control of the masters, but they were unable to establish an independent state. Shahrukhbi ibn Ashur Muhammad (d. 1709-1721), the chief of a thousand clans, was born in about 1669-1670 . However, his authority was not yet fully or completely independent of the Ashtarkhanids. Because in the sources Shahrukhbi's name is mentioned after Ashtarkhani Abulfayzkhan and it is mentioned that Shahrukhbi was given the title of father by the khan of Bukhara. Researchers' opinions on this are also controversial. In any case, Shah Rukhbi began to expand the lands under the rule of thousands of dynasties, trying to pursue a policy (albeit relatively) independently of the Bukhara khanate. During the reign of Shah Rukh, Kokand, Namangan, Margilan, Konibodom, Isfara and the surrounding villages were in the hands of thousands of dynasties. After the accession of Shah Rukhbi's son and successor, Muhammad Abdurahimbi (1721-1733), the lands under the rule of thousands began to expand again. Abdurahimbi conquered Andijan in 1724, Khojand in 1725, and Uratapa in 1726 and annexed them to the khanate. Although short-lived, he captured Samarkand and Kattakurgan in Bukhara and threatened Shahrissabz. Abdurahimbi founded a new city (first called Qalai Rahimbiy, then Kokand) in and around the village of Kokand (Khokand) and this city became the capital of the khanate .

Muhammad Abdul Karimbi ibn Shah Rukhbi, who ruled from 1733 to 1750, focused on defense. He built Isfara, Qatagan, Margilan, Haydarbek gates in Kokand, the capital of the khanate, and surrounded the city with a strong wall. At the same time, he dealt with the attacks of the Kalmyks

(Dzungars) on Fergana in 1741-1745. In the struggle against the Kalmyks, Abdul Karimbi relied on the help of the Kyrgyz-Kipchaks and the governor of Uratepa, Fazilbi, and maintained the independence of the khanate. After the death of Abdul Karimbi in 1750, his son Abdurahman ascended the khanate throne. However, he sat on the throne for nine months and then was sent to Margilan as governor, and Erdanabi, the second son of Abdurahimbi, ascended the throne. In 1753, under the pressure and demand of the Kalmyks, Bobobek ascended the throne of the khanate, which was held hostage by them. However, less than a year later, during the Uratepa march, Bobobek was killed in Besharik and Erdonabi (1755-1769) recaptured the Kokand throne. According to Chinese geographers, during his reign, in 1759-1760, Fergana was divided into four estates: Andijan, Namangan, Margilan and Kokand, among which Kokand was the leader. After Erdonabi, Sulaymonbek, the son of Shodibek, the third son of Shohruhbi, ascended the throne. Although he was greatly assisted in his conquest by the elders of the tribe, he ruled for only 6 months.

In 1770, Abdurahmanbi's son Norbotabi (1770-1801) ascended the throne of Kokand. Norbutabiy is relatively successful in consolidating Central wisdom and suppressing the resistance of disobedient rulers. After suppressing the uprisings in Chust and Namangan, he appointed his men to rule these cities. After several attempts, Norbutabi conquered Andijan, Osh, Khojand and neighboring areas. He also tried to conquer Tashkent in 1799, but his troops were defeated.

According to sources, during the reign of Umарkhan (1810-1822) the position of large landowners, military commanders and priests increased. He established a consistent order in the affairs of public administration, and regulated religious affairs. As a result, in 1818, with the consent of the clergy, Umарkhan received the title of "Amir al-Muslim" and gained both religious and secular authority. In general, by the middle of the 19th century, the political process and the internal situation in the Kokand Khanate had worsened. According to recent research, the reason for this is , firstly, that the Kipchaks, who are nomadic and semi-nomadic, did not recognize the authorities. Some provincial rulers in the khanate's territories rebelled against the Muslims. Secondly, there were mutual struggles among the Kipchaks to gain a high position in power and to influence the khan. Muslimquli, a descendant of the Kipchaks, also took an active part in these struggles. The third reason was the policy of the Kipchaks towards the settled population. The Kipchaks looked down on the settled population with contempt and discriminated against other ethnic groups. Fourthly , the external factor - the

gradual invasion of the Russian Empire into the territories of the khanate - led to a further intensification of political processes. By 1852, settled landowners and Tashkent aristocrats had gathered around Khudoyorkhan to fight the Muslims and the Kipchaks. With the help of these forces, Khudoyorkhan was unable to put an end to the struggle for the throne by killing the Muslim slave in 1853 and destroying his followers. In this situation, the internal situation of the khanate worsened, and it lagged far behind active foreign policy. In 1858, Mallakhon, the son of Sheralikhan's second wife, overthrew Khudoyorkhan and proclaimed himself khan. The revived group of nomads, led by the Kyrgyz Mallakhon and Alikuli, did not last long. It was members of this group who conspired against Mallakhon and killed him on February 25, 1863. Shahmurod, the son of Khudoyorkhan's brother Sarimsokbek, was enthroned. However, the commanders of the army and many of the officials in the palace conspired against him and sent for him, inviting him to sit on the throne again. At that time, Khudoyorkhan, who heard about Mallakhon's death, came to Jizzakh from Bukhara with the permission of Amir Muzaffar. With the help of Qanoat Shah, the governor of Turkestan, Khudoyorkhan, who had come to Tashkent from Jizzakh in March 1863, came to Khojand with the Tashkent army to march against Kokand. Meanwhile, Amir Muzaffar also came to Khojand with the Bukhara army. While Khudoyorkhan was planning to attack Kokand, on May 5, 1863, the townspeople opened the northern gates to him. As a result, the massacre began in Kokand, and Shah Murad Khan and his supporters fled to Margilan. Khudoyorkhan won the throne for the second time (1863). However, the Kyrgyz-Kipchaks of the khanate revolted around Kasan and Chust and attacked Turakurgan. They even sent letters to tribal leaders around Tashkent asking for help. As a result, the Kazakhs revolted around Tashkent and laid siege to Tashkent. The troops sent by Khudoyorkhan managed to suppress these revolts. However, the defeated Kyrgyz-Kipchak leaders continued to fight for the throne. In particular, Shodmonkhoja, Said Mahmudhantora, Alikuli under the leadership of Sultan Saidkhan came from Margilan and conquered Andijan and plundered the surrounding areas Balikchi, Kuva, Asaka, Shahrikhan, Osh, Poytug. On April 26, 1863, Sultan Said Khan's army came to Mingtut and laid siege to Kokand. Thanks to Amir Muzaffar's help to Khudoyorkhan, the Kyrgyz-Kipchak army went to Asaka and defended in the Karagulcha gorge. After fierce struggles, on July 24, 1863, Sultan Saidkhan ascended the throne of Kokand (1863-1865). Khudoyorkhan again fled to Bukhara. The internal conflicts in the khanate were extremely helpful to the external enemies. Taking advantage of this situation, Tsarist Russian troops occupied

Turkestan and Shymkent in 1864. In the spring of 1865, they approached Tashkent and captured Niyazbek Fortress. After a long siege, Tashkent was captured on June 17. In the summer of 1865, Khudoyorkhan, using the Sarosimals in Kokand, captured the Kokand throne for the last time with the help of the Emir's troops. After that, he no longer obeyed the emir's demands. Khudoyorkhan signed a trade agreement with Russia in January 1867, and an agreement with Kokand and Russia on February 13, 1868. From 1868 to 1873, Khudoyorkhan sent many gifts to Tashkent to improve relations with Russia. It also created favorable conditions for Russian traders. As a result, the Kokand Khanate became a de facto vassal of Russia. Although the relative peace that prevailed in the khanate lasted until 1873, as a result of the oppression of the ruler, his relatives and local governors, and the resurgence of the Kyrgyz-Kipchaks, internal conflicts and popular uprisings began. In particular, in 1873, Polatkhan (real name Mulla Ishaq Hasan oglu) was raised as a khan by the Kyrgyz, and a revolt broke out under his leadership. One of the influential officials in the palace, Abdurahman, conspired with Polatkhan in order to overthrow Khudoyorkhan, the sun, and to place his son, Sayyid Nasriddinbek, on the khan's throne, and revolted in the Horde. With the help of Sayyid Nasriddinbek Abdurahmon oftobachi, he was proclaimed khan (1875-1876). Khudoyorkhan abdicated in favor of Nasriddinbek and fled first to Khojand and then to Tashkent. Nasriddinbek's rise to power also failed to defuse the political situation in the country. Realizing this, Abdurahman Oftobachi decided to mobilize the population of the khanate to fight against Russia. However, in the face of fierce resistance from the Russians, he was defeated in a battle near Mahram. On September 25, 1875, when Polatkhan was about to attack Kokand in order to fight the Russians, Nasriddikhan made an agreement with the government of the Russian Empire. The news quickly spread throughout Kokand, and the population revolted again and attacked Orda. Nasriddin Khan left the throne and fled to Khojand. In Margilan, Polatkhan's army, which was mobilizing the population against the soldiers of the Russian Empire, was joined by citizens, madrassa students and representatives of the nomadic population. They were ordered to execute the winter and members of the khan's family who had collaborated with the invaders during the uprising.

was in Namangan at the time , began a complete conquest of the Kokand Khanate in February 1876 on the orders of the Russian Empire. Abdurahmon oftobachi and Polatkhan were arrested. Abdurahmon Oftobachi was exiled to Russia's Ekaterinoslav province, and Nasriddinkhan

was exiled to Vladimir province. Thus, on February 19, 1876, the Kokand Khanate, which had ruled for more than 150 years, was abolished, its territories were occupied by the Russian Empire, and the Fergana region was established in its place. Sources give various information about the population of the khanate. According to these data, the khanate (including Tashkent and Turkestan) had a population of 1 million in the early 19th century, 1.5-2 million in the mid-19th century, and 3 million in the second half of the 19th century. It is estimated that about 2 million people remained in the khanate's Fergana Valley as part of the invasion administration.

In the composition of the population, the sedentary population was more than the nomadic and semi-nomadic population. At the beginning of the 19th century, more than 40 percent of the population was nomadic and semi-nomadic, but by the end of that century, they were 15 percent. According to economic studies, the majority of the settled population was engaged in agriculture, handicrafts, handicrafts and trade, while the nomadic and semi-nomadic population was engaged in animal husbandry. The majority of the population of the Kokand Khanate is Uzbek, and Tajiks also live in the country's towns and villages. The khanate was also inhabited by Kyrgyz and Kipchaks. They lived nomadic and semi-nomadic life in the mountainous areas from the source of the Syrdarya to Lake Balkhash to the border with Kashgar, in the Ettisuv, Talas Valley, Alay Mountains, Badakhshan, Fergana Valley . In addition, Karakalpaks lived in the Fergana Valley, Kazakhs around Tashkent, nomadic Kazakhs in the eastern part of the khanate, in the deserts that separate the Kokand khanate from Bukhara and Russia. Although the development of handicrafts was the same in almost all towns and villages of the khanate, the production differed in some of its features, i.e., the type of product, the quality. Blacksmithing, jewelry, weaving, degreasing, pottery, coppersmithing and other branches of handicrafts were widely developed, and each city of the khanate was famous for its products produced in a certain field. For example, Kokand was famous for its jewelry and paper production, Shahri Khan and Chust for sewing and metalworking, in particular, knitting, Margilan, Namangan and Andijan for silk fabrics, and Tashkent for its sewing, weaving, cast iron and iron products. Production in the whole territory of the khanate was based on manual labor, the main occupations were weaving yarn and silk fabrics, making shoes, leather processing, making ceramics, blacksmithing, saddle making, painting, coppersmithing, jewelry, carpentry, carpentry, military weapons production, carving, waxing, pistachio coal making, embroidery, doping, knife-making, and so on. There were also workshops for gunpowder

and paper making belonging to the khan. Special attention is paid to armaments in the khanate. This industry is one of the most prestigious areas of urban handicraft production. Kokand is equipped with cannons, rifles, swords, knives, daggers, shields, spears and other military equipment. The main trade and commercial centers of the Kokand khanate are Kokand, Tashkent, Margilan, Andijan, Khojand, Namangan, Osh, Uratepa, among which Kokand is one of the trade centers not only of the khanate, but of Central Asia as a whole. According to the data, Kokand markets were distinguished by the richness of their products and the fact that the price was much cheaper than in other cities. The city's large walled markets have always been crowded with locals and foreign traders. According to Russian sources, in the 1920s there were six markets in Kokand, which were open on Sundays, Wednesdays and Thursdays. These markets are tightly controlled and betrayal of buyer rights is severely punished.

Foreign trade also played an important role in the economic life of the Kokand Khanate. The country has extensive trade relations with Bukhara, Khiva, Afghanistan, Iran, Turkey, India in the west and south, China in the east (via Kashgar), Dashti Kipchak nomads in the north, and especially Russia. Some sources mention that Japanese and British merchants also came to the khanate. The khanate exported mainly silk and silk fabrics, cotton, leather, precious stones, gold, silver, jewelry and other products. Imported mainly tea, metal, porcelain, household goods, ready-made fabrics, clothes, shoes and others.

The merchants of the khanate had regular trade relations with Bukhara and the cities on the borders of the emirate. The traders of both countries took an active part in the trade, and the Kokand traders brought to the Bukhara Emirate Russian iron, steel and cast iron, tobacco, handkerchiefs, rice and some Chinese or local silk fabrics, tea, porcelain. Indian tea, surp cloth, silk, dyes, opium (taryok), gold jewelry, yarn and cloth were brought to Kokand. Russian Chiti played a special role in Bukhara's trade with the Kokand Khanate. This fabric was brought from Orenburg or Petropavlovsk to Kazalinsk, and from there to Kokand via Bukhara, Samarkand and Khojand. The khanate also brought English fabrics from Mashhad, albeit small quantities of Kabul's tunics and turbans, and Indian attar goods. The Kokand khanate's trade relations with Kashgar were similar to those of the Bukhara emirate, with opium, porcelain, silver, Chinese silk fabrics, fiber, and carpets brought from Kashgar to Kokand. The subjugation of the Kazakh juzes to Russia led to the cessation of internecine wars between the ruling classes, which paved the way for trade relations in Central Asia, including the

Kokand khanate with Siberia, the Urals, and the Volga region. Kholik also has regular trade relations with India. According to sources, between 10,000 and 15,000 camels are shipped annually from India to Kokand, Tashkent, Bukhara and Kashgar via Kabul. Among them are yarn fabrics, silk, goat hair, horses and others. Horses were one of the most lucrative sources of trade . There are also reports that Indian merchants lived in the cities of the khanate and engaged in trade and even usury. Kokand-Russia trade relations also have a special place in Kokand's foreign relations. According to sources, the rapid development of Russian industry after 1861 and the growing demand for raw materials and foreign markets were one of the main reasons for Russia's active occupation of the Kokand market and its unlimited use. Iron, copper, steel, cast iron and iron products, chit and low-quality fabrics, small quantities of velvet , sugar, glass, leather, sheep and their skins, leather and leather products, felt from the Kazakh deserts, which are subject to Russia, were brought to Kokand from Russia. Cotton was mainly exported from the khanate to Russia.

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